

A Rhetorical Analysis of an Editorial: “The Hoodies of NWO”

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ABSTRACT: The present study is an attempt to identify the rhetorical pattern of an English editorial titled ‘the Hoodies of NWO’ published on October 8, 2011 in the Tehran Times –the most read English daily newspaper- in Iran. The theoretical framework of this analysis is based on the Systemic Functional (SF) theory of language and genre (Halliday & Hasan, 1989) which proposes a generic pattern namely generic structural potential (GSP) of text development for editorials. The data of the study were drawn from the above-mentioned editorial written by Hamid Golpira. The aim of the study is to identify the elements of generic structural potential (GSP), their sequence, and some rhetorical figures used throughout the editorial text. The findings revealed seven rhetorically structural elements which include three obligatory elements of Run-on Headline (RH), Addressing an Issue (AI), Argumentation (A) and four optional rhetorical elements such as Providing Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Concluding Remarks (CR), and Articulating a Solution (AS). A number of rhetorical organizational figures such as alliteration, allusion, anaphora, metonymy, analogy, parallelism, antithesis, meta-basis, epithet, zeugma, and parataxis were discovered as devices of influencing and persuading readers. Sequence wise, the following GSP was explored and formulated: $RH \wedge AI \wedge (BI) \wedge (IA) \wedge A \wedge (CR) \wedge (AS)$

Keywords: rhetorical figures; pattern; Generic Structural potential; editorial; epithet; analogy

1. INTRODUCTION

England, on August 6, erupted with the worst uprising and destruction seen since the legendary 1981 insurrection. Many people poured into the streets of Tottenham and marched in peace to condemn and protest against the shooting of a 29-year-old Duggan that took place on August 4. Later on the same day, the peaceful march detonated and deformed into mayhem after a 16-year-old girl was attacked and beaten by police. Of course some alleged she threw a rock at police while marchers said she was just seriously seeking to get her answers to why Mr. Duggan was shot dead. The uprising ended up with 5 deaths and 2000 arrests. Also over 1000 people were charged.

Igniting from Tottenham – where Duggan was shot dead- the chaos spread to several areas of England including Ponders End, Wood Green, Enfield Town, Brixton, Birmingham, Nottingham, Liverpool, Medway and Bristol.

This study aims to analyze an editorial titled ‘the Hoodies of NOW’ written on the London’s riots. The editorial was published in the Tehran Times – the most read English daily paper in Iran- last October. The present analysis is an endeavor to identify the rhetorical pattern and figures used throughout the editorial text.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In a study to explore the distinctive rhetorical features of English newspaper editorials, Ansary and Babaii (2004) applied Hallidayian approach to propose a generic pattern of text development for editorials. They collected 30 editorials from ‘Washington Times’ as representative of the

American newspapers. They found four obligatory elements (Run-on Headline, Addressing an Issue, Argumentation, and Articulating a Position) present in the 90% of the editorials in the sample. Optional elements in the editorials were providing Background Information (BI), which either preceded Addressing an Issue (AI) or followed it, Initiation of Argumentation (IA) which, in some cases, was necessary to help writers start off their arguments, and Closure of Argumentation (CA) which sometimes used to round off the arguments.

Katajamaki and Koskelain (2007) studied the rhetorical structure of editorials in English, Swedish and Finnish business newspapers: *Financial Times*, *Dagens Industri*, and *Taloussanommat*. They sought to answer the following questions: first, if there was a typical rhetorical structure for the editorials in business newspapers irrespective of national and cultural features; second, if there were different types; and third, what factors were connected to the content of the text, language and culture which would correlate with the different types. The material of the study consisted of 22 editorials from these three business newspapers. As a starting point for their analysis, they used a modification of Van Dijk’s (1993) view of the rhetorical structure of editorials. Van Dijk (1993) quoted in Katajamaki and Koskelain (2007: 2) divides editorials into three sections each having specific stage(s) and function. The stages are the introductory section, the intermediate section which in turn is divided into a) the reason section, evidence or examples, and b) the solution section, and the coda section which is the closing section.

The present study hence tries to identify the rhetorical pattern and figures used in a single editorial. This rhetorical

study is limited to one editorial text culled from the Tehran Times English daily paper.

3. METHOD

3.1. Material and Procedure

The study has followed the systematic functional model – taken from the systematic functional theory- used in Halliday and Hasan (1989), Ghadessy (1993), Paltridge (1993) Henry and Roseberry (1997), Ansary (2004), Ansary and Babaie (2004) and Hodges (2006). Systemic, or Systemic-Functional, (SF) theory has its origins in the main intellectual tradition of European linguistics that developed following the work of Saussure. The SF theory is functional and semantic rather than formal and syntactic in orientation. This theory takes the text rather than the sentence as its object, and defines its scope by reference to usage rather than grammaticality. In the first stage of the SF model, the macro-rhetorical structure (GSP) of the editorials as a sub-genre of the newspaper genre was to be identified in an editorial titled ‘ the Hoodies of NWO’ written by Hamid Golpira and published in the Tehran Times daily newspaper in Iran (See appendix for the original version.). Notably, the editorial text was culled from the Tehran Times online website: www.tehrantimes.com. Next, the sequence of such rhetorically structural elements would be presented. In addition, the researcher has looked into the editorial text to find out rhetorical organizational figures as well as the author’s intent to use them. These figures (or devices) which include allusion, anaphora, synecdoche, climax, to mention but a few, will be defined later in the analysis section.

The Tehran Times is the most read English newspaper which was established in 1979 as an affiliate to the Islamic Propagation Organization. Among its first-day purposes has been the echoing of the message of Islamic republic of Iran into the world. The Tehran Times is an English-language daily newspaper based in Tehran, Iran. Its website could be approachable online through the URL ‘www.tehrantimes.com’.

3.2. Newspaper Editorials as a Sub-Genre

Newspaper editorial articles are regarded as the large class of opinion discourse which is considered a newspaper sub-genre these days (van Dijk, 2005). Unlike other newspaper subgenres including the news reports and advertisements that present evaluations and comments about the news events already reported, editorials tend to argue or persuade their audiences. In other words, the main objective of editorials is to influence the readers to accept their intended interpretation of the news events. Thus, editorials are considered to contain rhetoric imbedded in them. These rhetorical patterns or conventions might diversify from language to language.

Reah (2002. p: 106) stresses the importance of editorial texts. Reah believes that editorial writers express the

information in an explicit or implicit way which is usually affected by certain rhetoric and ideology they stick to. It is also a powerful way to influence the readers as the editorial readers usually tend to not examine the truth value of the hidden or indirectly expressed information. Editorial writers, then, tend to employ this textual strategy to convey their intended meaning without, of course, directly asserting it.

3.3. Generic structure potential

The theoretical framework of this analysis is based on the Systemic Functional (SF) theory of language and genre (Halliday & Hasan, 1989). Hasan describes the generic structure potential of a particular genre as being a description or ‘the total range of textual structures available within a genre (Hasan 1984a 79).’ To be capable of this, a model of the generic structure potential must specify those elements whose presence appears obligatory to the particular genre, and those elements which appear optional for the particular genre, as well as the ordering of the elements in relation to each other, including the possibility of recursion (Hasan 1984a).

Linking the systematic functional (SF) approach to text analysis, Halliday and Hasan (1989: 63-65) introduced the concept of “Generic Structure Potential (GSP) “ for any specific contextual configuration to define a genre. For example, in order to identify the obligatory and optional rhetorical elements of „Service Encounter“ texts, they examined a set of similar spoken texts in this regard and established the GSP of the „Shop Transaction“ genre as follows:

[(G).(SI)^][(SE.) {SR^SC^} ^S^] P^PC (^F)

The above GSP shows that any shop transaction in English potentially consists of the following macro-structural elements: Greeting (G), followed by Sale Initiation (SI), Sale Enquiry (SE), Sale Request (SR), Sale Compliance (SC), Sale (S), Purchase (P), Purchase Closure (PC), and Finish (F).

Following Hasan's framework for analysis, this rhetorical study aimed to identify the structural elements of the texts, their textual sequence as well as the rhetorical figures used throughout the editorial text (Hasan 1989a).

3.4. Rhetoric and Rhetorical Figures

Rhetoric is the art of persuasion through written, oral, or visual means. The idea of rhetoric has been around since the classical days. Great works on this subject still exist from the classical period. Some of the greatest speakers and speeches from history were written by people with a great knowledge of rhetoric – for example John F Kennedy, Winston Churchill. Some of the famous figures or tropes one has probably heard of are Irony, anaphora, epithet, alliteration, and polysyndeton. It is to be noted that grammar is the science of good writing; rhetoric the art.

4. ANALYSIS

4.1. Rhetorical Pattern and Figures

The analysis of the editorial text is sequenced from excerpt 1 to excerpt 9. The excerpts are indented to stand out. Each excerpt is followed by its respective analysis which contains qualitative explanations and comments on the rhetorical elements and figures of speech found in it. The first excerpt along with its analysis is presented as follows:

Excerpt1: the Hoodies of the NWO (the title of the editorial)

Headlines generally set the themes and topics of a text. Van Dijk (1988: 248) explains that headlines “define the overall coherence or semantic unity of discourse, and also what information readers memorize best from a news report”.

So as to excerpt 1, the word ‘Hoodies’ not only is used to simply refer to a person who wears a hood, but to employ allusion. The Oxford Advanced Learner’s dictionary (eighth edition) defines allusion as an indirectly quick reference to a person or subject. The author cleverly uses a quick flash back to the Robin hood mythology who has been marked with robbery as well as outlawed heroism on one hand and doing good as to feeding the poor, on the other. Unlike David Cameron –the leader of Conservative party- who once said that the hoodie is worn more for defensive than offensive purposes, the Iranian author tries to altercast the hoodie wearers -as aliens- by attributing them anonymity, wrongdoing, mystery, and offensiveness. Francis (1979) in defining altercasting, says “when there is a conflict between two collectivities, rhetoricians may vary the degree of perceived enmity by their characterization of the opposition. If the latter is described as malevolent and lacking any human qualities in common with one’s own side, then the characterization would be alien”. This explanation seems true about the ‘hoodies’. In line with the concept of ‘hoodie’ Angela McRobbie, professor of communications at Goldsmiths College in the UK, says “the appeal of the ‘hoodie’ is because of its promise of anonymity, mystery and anxiety”.

Also the abbreviation “NWO” is deemed preferred to the full phrase ‘New World Order’ in the headline as to create more suspense and drive the audience to de-abbreviate. Figure 1 will summarize the above analysis.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS
1	Allusion and altercasting	Run-on Headline (RH)	obligatory

Figure 1: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt1

Excerpt2: Last August, everyone was saying, “London’s burning, the hoodies are burning the town down.”

The direct quote used in excerpt 2, “might function as a way of constructing the authenticity and objectivity of the statement. It thus seemingly absolves the writer’s own opinions and it is a technique of disguising the incursion of the writer’s own ideological tendency in the reported speech.” (Merskin 2004: 366)

In other words, the above statement uses a quote with the generalized, indefinite pronoun ‘everyone’. The pronoun ‘everyone’ shows a general nonspecific reference to people especially when they are unclear, unknown, or when the author refuses to name them. The direct quote in excerpt 2 actually boosts the author’s credibility and trustworthiness (ethos) in the eyes of the public despite its source is clouded with the collective noun – ‘everybody’.

In the quote above, the author covers passivity – London is burning- followed by activity – the hoodies are burning- through the zeugma trope in parallel with no conjunction word which proves the application of zeugma. Zeugma, based on Merriam Webster dictionary, is “the use of a word to modify or govern two or more words usually in such a manner that it applies to each in a different sense or makes sense with only one”. So, using zeugma, the author might mean to condense four sentential segments – three clauses + an adverbial phrase – within a single statement sentence for the purposes of easiness, shortness, repetition reduction, and juxtaposition of the notions put forward.

The proper noun ‘London’ in excerpt 2 is metonymically crafted. ‘London’ is used to refer to its streets, cars, building, and so forth. The artful use of metonymy seems to deliberately trigger the dramatization and enlargement of the cause as if an attempt is made to change the concept word of ‘matter’ into ‘issue’ as one could coin the term ‘issuization’ which connotes to making an issue of an event intentionally. It is to make clear that metonymy is a rhetorical figure or strategy in which one word or phrase is substituted for another with which it is closely associated. The Marriam Webster dictionary defines metonymy as: “a figure of speech consisting of the use of the name of one thing for that of another of which it is an attribute or with which it is associated”.

Lastly, the above statement could be strongly associated with the articulation of an issue (AI). The issue – the unrest in London- set off within this statement sentence and will predictably continue to unwrap. The AI serves as a motivation for the editorial. In other words, it indicates that there exists an issue which must be debated. The issue is often an important current socio-political topic that must necessarily be discussed and is sometimes resolved. This is the second obligatory element found in the editorial whose existence is absolutely obligatory. AI in normal cases may precede some background information about the debated problem. The below figure illustrates and summarizes the above explanations.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS

2	Parallelism, zeugma, metonymy, and ethos	Addressing an Issue (AI)	Obligatory
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Figure 2: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt 2

Excerpt3: The unrest began in London on August 6 after a peaceful march held to protest against a fatal shooting by the Metropolitan Police on August 4, in which Mark Duggan, a 29-year-old Black man, was killed. The unrest rapidly spread to other cities in Britain.

A fine combination of a) antithesis, b) anaphora, and c) climax are conspicuous. These terms are defined in the Marriam Webster dictionary as a) the rhetorical contrast of ideas by means of parallel arrangements of words, clauses, or sentences, b) repetition of a word or expression at the beginning of successive phrases, clauses, sentences, or verses especially for rhetorical or poetic effect, and c) a figure of speech in which a series of phrases or sentences is arranged in ascending order of rhetorical forcefulness. In excerpt 3, the words ‘unrest, protest, fatal, killed,’ are the explicit antithesis of the word ‘peaceful’ while the victimized word ‘Black’ is considered the implicit antithesis of ‘Police’ who are almost all white-skinned. Doing so, the author manages to appeal to the pathos of the audiences and drive them into the realm of mercifulness and pitifulness.

Both the elaborate opening and succinct closing clauses begin with the same phrase ‘the unrest’ - an obvious anaphoric strategy. Also the background above is narrated in such lucidity that ends with the climax of ‘unrest pandemic throughout Britain’ in a try a) to signpost the end of the providing background information (BI) and b) to prepare the pathos-filled audiences for the next scene (probably the argumentation). BI, an optional rhetorical element, usually makes reference to a place, thing, or situation. It is the rhetorical device which gives readers some background on the major issue(s) that are addressed in the text. It is essentially a description whose purpose is to set the scene for later development of the topic.

Figure 3 better shows the analysis.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS
3	Anaphora, antithesis, climax, and pathos	Providing background Information (BI)	Optional

Figure 3: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt 3

Excerpt4: From the very beginning, there was a division between protesters who wanted to stage peaceful demonstrations and those who were in favor of violence. For some of the violent protesters, the violence was an

authentic outburst of outrage. Others were hooligans with no real political views who decided to avail themselves of the opportunity to do a bit of looting and burning and vandalism. However, it seems there was a third group among the violent protesters who were actually agent provocateurs goading people on to commit acts of violence.

Excerpt 4 applies the rhetorical figure of epithet. The Marriam Webster dictionary offers a definition for the term ‘epithet’ as: “characterizing word or phrase accompanying or occurring in place of the name of a person or thing”. The epithet is demonstrated in the phrase ‘authentic outburst of outrage’ in which the attribute ‘authentic’ is associated with the personified inanimate word ‘outburst’.

It should be noted that the third group of protesters is in antithesis with the other two groups i.e. peaceful protesters and violent protesters. The engaged groups i.e. government-charged agent protesters vs. non-agent protesters are dichotomized through the use of the coordinator ‘and’ using zeugmatic strategy. Later on, the third and focused group of trained forces in hoods is introduced. These were seemingly designated by their government and attributed to the commitment of vandalism.

The author seems to have undergone altercasting the third group of protesters as alienated and malevolent. The above extract in part, provides background information (BI) for the initiation of the argument that will come consequently. Figure 4 illustrates the GSP elements and rhetorical figures used in excerpt 4.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS
4	Antithesis, epithet, zeugma, and altercasting	Providing Background Information (BI)	Optional

Figure 4: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt4

Excerpt5: Of course, this will seem like an outrageous charge to most people. After all, why would the British authorities want to enlist agents provocateurs to encourage people to loot and burn?

Excerpt 5 makes use of epithet. The quality adjective of ‘outrageous’ now modifies the inanimate noun ‘charge’. A non-rhetorical question is also posed which contains a few harsh words in a row – provocateurs, loot, and burn - using zeugma. The author’s stance is now so overt. He as if tries to ignite an argumentation fast and loose.

Argumentation uses linguistic cues to justify or refute a standpoint, with the aim of securing views in agreement. Specifically, propositions are put forward as claims (made by the writer or others) and sometimes, evidence or reasons

are presented as justification and/or refutation of those claims.

The author creates an adjacently sharp contrast between a statement (of course this will seem) and a question (After all why would ...?). The up-to-now voiceless author has thrown his argumentation using a provocative question which is really non-rhetorical rather than rhetorical.

He also charges the British Government authorities with outlawed acts such as looting and burning. He uses the verb ‘enlist’ which indicates multiplicity of items on a list. He simply says the plain-clothed or hooded agents are not a few.

Figure 5 sheds light on the analysis.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS
5	Epithet and zeugma	Initiation of Argumentation (IA)	Optional

Figure 5: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt5

Excerpt 6: Britain currently has more surveillance cameras monitoring its citizens than any other country. Britain is the most surveillance country in the world. And the New World Order will be a total surveillance society.

The focal word ‘Britain’ is used twice to display anaphora. The intent might be the attraction of the eyes of readers to the Britain as a wrongdoer. The anaphora fluidly progress toward a climax where the main debate is positioned i.e. the last sentence. The last sentence – a paraphrased statement - shows the central message against which the author has been positioned his stronghold.

Excerpt 6 is deemed to be an answer to the question in excerpt 5. In addition, excerpt 6 puts on display nucleus-satellite relationship in which the last sentence is considered nucleus while the first two ones are regarded as satellite positioned to provide evidence and introduction to the nucleus. The nucleus also is detached from the rest of the excerpt to absorb more attention. According to the Marriam Webster dictionary, nucleus refers to “a central point, group, or mass about which gathering, concentration, or accretion takes place” while satellite means “someone or something attendant, subordinate, or dependent”.

The use of alliteration in the phrase ‘surveillance society’ is apparent. Alliteration, based on the Marriam Webster dictionary is “the repetition of usually initial consonant sounds in two or more neighboring words or syllables”. The alliteration aims to help audiences read with ease and perhaps enables them to grasp the peeled argued point quickly. Figure 6 demonstrates the GSP elements and rhetorical figures used in excerpt 6.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
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		ELEMENT	STATUS
6	Anaphora, alliteration, detachment, nucleus-satellite relationship	Argumentation (A)	Obligatory

Figure 6: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt 6

Excerpt7: U.S. officials made similar remarks after 9/11. They said that surveillance had to be increased, everyone’s phone had to be bugged, everyone’s mail had to be read, everyone’s emails and other electronic communications had to be monitored, and U.S. citizens would have to give up some of the rights guaranteed to them in the U.S. Constitution in order to increase their safety.

In other words, “We will be taking away your liberty in order to safeguard your liberty.”

The author draws an analogy between Britain’s status quo and that of American’s troubled situation a decade back. His objective is to show the degree of suffocation in both countries with big focus on the Britain situation. The Cambridge English dictionary defines the term analogy as “a comparison between things which have similar features, often used to help explain a principle or idea”.

The repetition of the collective pronoun ‘everyone’ demonstrates the application of anaphora which in some point gives parallelism and beauty. Parallelism in the Marriam Webster dictionary is defined as “repeated syntactical similarities introduced for rhetorical effect”.

The US’s controlling the liberty and privacy receives attention. The subjective pronoun ‘they’ is used with no clear antecedent. ‘They’, as an exclusive out-grouped pronoun, refers to the US officials in general and there is no specificity to strengthen the so called quoted claimed evidence.

Excerpt 7 holds an indirect quote followed by a direct one. Hence the ‘voice’ of that statement belongs to the writer, and not of the US officials. According to Merskin (2004) indirect quotes “enable the reporter to represent the information in the way that he wants to represent transforming the speech structurally yet retaining what he wants and excluding what he does not want in the discourse.” On the other hand, direct quotes “function as a way of constructing the authenticity and objectivity of the statement, thus seemingly absolving the writer’s own opinions” and it is a technique of “disguising the incursion of the writer’s own ideological tendency in the reported speech” Merskin (2004).

Finally the discrepancy between UK and US citizens becomes conspicuous as the earlier ones are active protesters; the later passive. Figure 7 is an illustration of the analysis.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
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		ELEMENT	STATUS
7	Analogy and parallelism	Argumentation (A)	Obligatory

Figure 7: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt 7

Excerpt 8: And the New World Order will be a lot worse than Margaret Thatcher. The New World Order will be a total surveillance society and a total control society.

Excerpt 8 employs a comparative adjective – worse – to show the severity degree of the status quo compared to the less severe era during the time of Margaret Thatcher (an example of analogy). The phrase ‘Margaret Thatcher’ also is used metonymically to refer to her line of thought, policy or order. This phrase reminds the audiences of a great British figure who seems to have an upper hand in – at least- the British policy which seems to be the intent of the author.

Anaphora is also featured in excerpt 8. The clause (the new world order will) is delicately repeated for better echoing the central message in both excerpted sentences.

Zeugma is furthermore showcased through the use of the coordinating conjunction ‘and’ to form a sentence-to-sentence link – as in the first sentence of the excerpt and its preceding one (‘And the New World’). ‘And’ also causes a phrase-to-phrase connection – as in the second sentence of the excerpt (‘a total surveillance society and total control society’) in excerpt 8.

In whole the above sharpened extract (excerpt 8) serves to offer concluding remarks (CR). CR as one of the last categories summarizes the whole editorial (Babaei , 2009). It acts as a conclusion and wraps up the editorial. Its presence in the editorial is of no obligation though. CR thus comes up to summarize and remind the reader of the main debated claims. The appearance of these elements [GSP obligatory and optional elements] in a specific order corresponds to our perception of whether the text is

complete or incomplete (Halliday and Hasan, 1989: 62). Figure 8 sheds light on the analysis.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS
8	Analogy, anaphora, zeugma and metonymy	Concluding Remarks (CR)	Optional

Figure 8: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt 8

Excerpt 9: If we want to avoid such a dystopian future, we better start thinking 20 moves ahead on the geopolitical chessboard.

The editorial writer switches to use the plural pronoun ‘we’ other than the plural third person pronoun ‘they’ with the intents of a) melting down into the in-group community and b) powering on his loudspeaker and c) making the readers support the oppressed. In other words, using two similar subjective pronouns- we -, the author merges himself with his audiences. He tries to show they both have commonalities one of which is being the dwellers of the world under full CCTV. The ‘we’ can be classified as an inclusive in-group and according to Macionis (2001: 169), an in-group is “a social group commanding a member’s esteem and loyalty,” whilst an out-group (‘they’) is ‘a social group toward which one feels competition or opposition.’ Tajfel (1982 in Macionis 2001: 169-170) states that, members of an ingroup would usually have positive views of themselves but hold negative views of the ‘outgroup.’ (See figure 9.)

The author is also trying to mitigate the acidity level of his sharp argumentation which may in result agitate his addressees- British and U.S. hegemonies or governments. Figure 9 demonstrates the members of the in-group and out-group.

Figure 9: Members of the in-group and out-group

Excerpt 9 uses a conditional sentence – ‘If we want ...’ – to demonstrate that there exists a real situation that is still required to be resolved.

According to Shokouhi and Amin (2010) “Editorials can be categorized into two groups: those which contain the element “AS” and those which do not. The editorials which do not include this element, that is editorials written to discuss some views without resolving a problem. In excerpt

9, a stinging solution is offered (Articulation of a Solution or AS). AS specifies the writer’s solution for the debated problem and how it can be resolved. As was found, the editorial’s task is not only to discuss an issue but also to suggest a solution for the debated problem.

Figure 10 shows the analysis of excerpt 9.

Excerpt NO.	RHETORICAL FIGURE	GSP	
		ELEMENT	STATUS
9	Zeugma	Articulation of a Solution(AS)	Optional

Figure 10: Rhetorical analysis of excerpt 9

4.2. Sequence

In light of sequence, the below formula has been elicited from the analysis:

$$RH \wedge AI \wedge (BI) \wedge (IA) \wedge A \wedge (CR) \wedge (AS)$$

In the above formula, the round brackets indicate optionality of the enclosed elements. Therefore the Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Concluding Remarks (CR), and Articulating a solution (AS) are optional and Run-on Headline (RH), Articulating an Issue (AI), Argumentation (A) are obligatory – the backbone of the editorial. The caret sign (^) shows the sequence. Violation of sequence in the above GSP can bring disorder to that section of a text, hence hard to follow.

5. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Findings of the present paper clearly demonstrate that there existed seven rhetorical elements in the structure of the editorial text: Run-on Headline (RH), Addressing an Issue (AI), Argumentation (A), Providing Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Concluding Remarks (CR), and Articulating a Solution (AS). Therefore, (RH), (AI), and (A) are obligatory since their existence in the text is really inevitably essential while (BI), (IA), (CR), (AS) are considered optional elements whose presence just better empower the argumentation in the GSP. Sequence wise, the following GSP was formulated.

$$RH \wedge AI \wedge (BI) \wedge (IA) \wedge A \wedge (CR) \wedge (AS)$$

It is worth noting that it might happen to see more than one argument to debate a single issue. The editorial centers on the point that the New World Order will be a total surveillance society. In this respect, two arguments constituted the main argumentation. The author first brought in the case of violence and upheaval in England followed by the second argument which embodied the insurrection and uprising in the U.S. Both arguments shared the single issue of the future total surveillance society. The author detoured back to the first argument – the England’s uprising. In other words, the argumentation of the editorial contains two arguments in two different contexts: England and the U.S. The author wisely begins with the England’s violence, flows into the US uprising and finally turns back to England. The debated cause has remained unchangeable though.

As shown earlier in the analysis section, the text was analyzed based on the rhetorical structure model (GSP) of the editorials as a sub-genre of the newspaper genre and rhetorical figures. Following Halliday and Hasan (1989), Ghadessy (1993), Paltridge (1993) Henry and Roseberry (1997), Ansary (2004), Ansary and Babaii (2004) and Hodges (2006) who have adopted the GSP model, this study has identified the same rhetorical elements as Run-on Headline (RH), Addressing an Issue (AI), Argumentation (A), Providing Background Information (BI), Initiation of Argumentation (IA), Concluding Remarks (CR), and Articulating a Solution (AS). The elements (RH), (AI), and (A) are obligatory while (BI), (IA), (CR), and (AS) are optional in the text. The only difference found between the GSP explored by previous works cited above and that of the current paper is the sequence of the last two elements – (CR) and (AS) positions. In the other words, (CR) precedes (AS) in the GSP of the present study whereas in the GSP of the previous works cited above, (CR) is preceded by (AS).

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APPENDIX

Tehran Times - [TehranTimes.com]

Leading International Daily

Hoodies of the NWO - Tehran Times

Hamid Golpira

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Last August, everyone was saying, "London's burning, the hoodies are burning the town down."

Since then, there has been much commentary about what really happened, but it seems that most commentators have missed a couple of key points.

The unrest began in London on August 6 after a peaceful march held to protest against a fatal shooting by the Metropolitan Police on August 4, in which Mark Duggan, a 29-year-old Black man, was killed.

The unrest rapidly spread to other cities in Britain.

What began as a demonstration to protest against a single incident of police brutality quickly became a mini-uprising against discrimination, institutionalized racism, poverty, unemployment, stratified class divisions, and social injustice.

From the very beginning, there was a division between protesters who wanted to stage peaceful demonstrations and those who were in favor of violence.

For some of the violent protesters, the violence was an authentic outburst of outrage.

Others were hooligans with no real political views who decided to avail themselves of the opportunity to do a bit of looting and burning and vandalism.

However, it seems there was a third group among the violent protesters who were actually agents provocateurs goading people on to commit acts of violence.

Of course, this will seem like an outrageous charge to most people. After all, why would the British authorities want to enlist agents provocateurs to encourage people to loot and burn?

Well, first of all, through such a move they were able to discredit peaceful protesters with legitimate grievances and make them look like common criminals.

In addition, the chaos provided a good excuse for the British government to increase social control mechanisms.

Britain currently has more surveillance cameras monitoring its citizens than any other country.

Britain is the most surveilled country in the world.

And the New World Order will be a total surveillance society.

Shortly after the unrest began, British officials said that video images recorded by surveillance cameras would be used to identify rioters for prosecution.

Tellingly, they also called for increased surveillance, arguing that it would be necessary to prevent a recurrence of such events and to protect law-abiding citizens and their property.

Always beware when you hear phrases like "to protect law-abiding citizens and their property."

When government officials make such remarks, they are actually saying, "We will be taking away some of your

rights, especially your right to privacy, in order to increase your security."

Or, in other words, "In order to safeguard your rights, we will be taking away some of your rights."

U.S. officials made similar remarks after 9/11.

They said that surveillance had to be increased, everyone's phone had to be bugged, everyone's mail had to be read, everyone's emails and other electronic communications had to be monitored, and U.S. citizens would have to give up some of the rights guaranteed to them in the U.S. Constitution in order to increase their safety.

In other words, "We will be taking away your liberty in order to safeguard your liberty."

And most U.S. citizens went along with it with no complaints like good little sheeple, or, more accurately, like sheeple to the slaughter.

In the book *An Historical Review of the Constitution and Government of Pennsylvania*, which was published in 1759, the eighteenth century U.S. statesman Benjamin Franklin wrote:

"Those who would give up essential liberty to purchase a little temporary safety deserve neither liberty nor safety."

Perhaps U.S. citizens should spend some time reflecting on this famous quote.

The discontented hooded youth of Britain involved in the unrest would be horrified to learn that they were being used as pawns to facilitate the establishment of a New World Order that would

be a total surveillance society.

They would probably prefer to laugh about the remarks of the pundits who said, "The protesters should be recognized as the legitimate government of Britain."

But that's never going to happen, and the truth of the matter is that they were being used as pawns of the NWO.

The political activists of Britain and the rest of the world have to wake up to the fact that the powers that be think 20 moves ahead on the geopolitical chessboard.

The Machiavellian machinations of the mandarins of masonry are subtle and can only be discerned by the most astute observers.

In the late 1970s, there was also unrest in Britain, but it did not lead to a progressive change in the political order.

Quite the contrary, the unrest galvanized right-wing voters, who came to the polls in droves, while many progressives did not bother to vote, and Britain got stuck with Margaret Thatcher for 11 years.

And the New World Order will be a lot worse than Margaret Thatcher.

The New World Order will be a total surveillance society and a total control society.

If we want to avoid such a dystopian future, we better start thinking 20 moves ahead on the geopolitical chessboard.

AUTOBIOGRAPHY

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